

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: OBODO-OBUNSELI****FIRST NAME: RACHAEL****PROGRAM CODE: DGG****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The author used Turabian style (in-text/parenthetical)

The author used Zotero to insert references

The author used Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is 0%

The author used MSWord 2013 on Windows 11Pro

List of key concepts within the Response paper

1. Essay Composition (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 6–14)
2. Punctuation (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 15–23)
3. UK versus US English usage (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 24–32)
4. Plagiarism (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 33–39)
5. Adherence to Style Conventions (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 40–42)
6. Latin Abbreviations and Expressions (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 58–64)
7. Paper Review Process (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 65)

INTERNATIONAL ACADEMIC WRITING (DOCTORATE)

1) INTRODUCTION

The International Academic Writing course centres on the skills and methods necessary for composing academic papers at an acceptable international standard. It is structured into seven periods, and in my response paper, I will focus on period one, which covers the fundamental principles of academic writing. An attempt has been made to further simplify the contents of the course pack into seven key concepts. I will review the ACA-401/401D (period 1) course pack and the introductory ACA-401 tutorial video materials to elucidate the highlighted key concepts and seek clarifications in areas that seem difficult to comprehend.

2) KEY CONCEPTS

After carefully reviewing the key concepts highlighted, I have realised that there is room for improvement in my writing skills. Having concluded an undergraduate degree

and a master's degree with a distinction (first class) grade, I find the methodology in this course quite expository and valuable to attain a standard skill required for completing my Doctoral degree and beyond. One thing I found particularly helpful was the course reinforcement of standard essay composition skills and the emphasis on keeping writing simple. Also, one new technique for me as a Law graduate is using the Turabian referencing style. The key concepts will be explained below.

a) Essay Composition

In this course, academic writing is the main topic discussed. As I have seen, the number one rule is that planning your writing as soon as possible is a bedrock for successful essay writing. Even though I had planned my writing, one missing piece was the time frame I allocated to each task. Sometimes, deadlines are a motivating factor for my writing. The study material emphasises that to effectively plan for and complete an essay; one must take into consideration the following.

- Starting early, deciding what to write, forming my ideas and thoughts on the research topic, and drafting the initial strategy to write the essay are the first things I will note when I have a writing task. A proper comprehension of what kind of essay is required at this stage;
- Researching the topic I have decided to write on involves critical and creative thinking. I would have a reading list that is relevant to my research topic;
- The next vital part is organising my ideas to reflect precisely what is required for my writing. I understand that the success of this stage will significantly reflect how the essay turns out in the end. This, in other words, is the frame of the leading writing;
- The format of my essay should include an introduction, body, and conclusion. I believe this is what is referred to as the first draft;
- As a rule in academic writing, an essay must contain a reference. In this case, I would use the Turabian style, which Euclid has approved for response papers;
- Before handing in my essay, the general expectation is that detailed editing should have taken place. A neutral editor may be needed to ensure the essay ideas are not lopsided. I should ensure the essay is turned in to the correct examiner and through the right channel and conclusively; and
- Thumb rules to note in essay writing include stating my main argument from the beginning, remaining focused, avoiding general sweeping statements, writing in simple language, avoiding cumbersome statements, providing evidence for any claims, ensuring my views are arguable, and giving credit to referenced literature (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 6–14).

b) Punctuation

The one essential thing I should note when it comes to punctuation is to keep its usage at a minimum. This course package has given me clarity as to the correct meaning and application of some punctuation. The ‘defining’ commas stood out for me the most (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 19). I have used commas without understanding the varying rules guiding them in the past, as long as the sentence sounded readable. Also, I now understand that full stops should not be used with a question mark or exclamation at the end of a sentence (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 22). As I engage the study material for this course, it is now laughable how I have used double quotation for just any quote I refer to. I have realised that a double quotation is used when you need to quote within the initial quote.

c) UK versus US English Usage

My English education background stems from my country’s (Nigeria) school curriculum, which recognises and approves the use of the British English language. This must have been based on Nigeria being in the past within the British Colony. British language has been my preferred language, except otherwise stipulated by my examiner. Generally speaking, television and social media have made most people use British and US English interchangeably. For example, I used the same concepts in the past, with words like ‘bank holiday (UK) and public holiday (US)’ and ‘hire and rent.’ This course material further reiterates my understanding of using consistent language, which is critical in this case. I have unintentionally used both languages in the past in one writing. For example, the word ‘behaviour’, is spelt in the US as ‘behavior’. As the study tutorial video explained, Euclid has made available Grammarly software that automatically makes it much easier to spot and correct in my preferred language (Cleenewerck 2016). Further, the study material does not dwell so much on the differences but on the similarities of both languages. Words like ‘aluminium’ and ‘aluminum’ are the same terms but with different spellings and similar pronunciations. Another important thing I noted in the study material is the use of punctuation, which is the least talked about but the most essential difference in both languages. The UK style uses ‘inverted commas’, while the US uses “quotation marks”(Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 24–32). For example, ‘John fell off the chair and shouted “help”, but no one came’ (this style portrays quotation within a quotation). The US example would be, “John fell off the chair and shouted ‘help’, but no one came”. Punctuation outside the quote is the UK style, whereas the US applies punctuation inside the quote. ‘Does Kirsty have a job?’ (UK); “Does Kirsty have a job?” (US). There are things to note that are different in the two languages: dates, punctuations in a formal business letter, informal letters, and punctuations in titles. For example, ‘Dear Mr. Paul:’ for US and ‘Dear Mr Paul,’ for UK (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 32). From the exhilarating insights unveiled in the study material, I am suddenly urged to rewrite my previous papers (published and unpublished).

d) Plagiarism

One of the foremost things I learnt as a law graduate is that plagiarism carries a criminal liability in most jurisdictions. EUCLID has emphasised the importance of avoiding plagiarism and exhaustively explains the various forms it may take. The study material quotes that:

‘Taking someone else’s words or ideas, such as quoting, paraphrasing, copying, and pasting from the internet and not giving credit to the author. Having someone write a paper for you, then putting your name on it, and giving it to your professor would be plagiarism’ (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 34).

The above quote implies that when I intend to engage any idea or work of literature, I am responsible for giving appropriate and recommended credit to the authors. Regarding writing essays, one should note when to give credit, ensure ethical considerations, understand how to cite the source, and when not to cite (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 34–37). Where the idea is common knowledge and in the public domain, I am not required or obliged to cite the source. How I cite largely depends on the style I am using. In this case, EUCLID has recommended in-text citations and a list of references at the end of the essay (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 35).

e) Adherence to Style Conventions

As the name implies, style is the approach I would take to do my essay. Usually, an examiner’s recommended style is preferred. The critical factor here is consistency in using the particular style throughout the essay. EUCLID has approved the Chicago Rules (Turabian style) for response papers. The American English has been approved as the preferred proofing language. The British language is also acceptable, which is my preference because of my background. As explained in the study material, the lack of a consistent and approved style in writing leaves room for debate on the elements in the style used. Now, I understand the elements that make up a style, which is an inexhaustible list. They include preferred sentence lengths, manuscript layout, font usage, depth of treatment of a subject, spelling (UK-behaviour v US- Behavior, for example), readership considerations, use of abbreviations, accepted terminology, the use of symbols, voice preferences (active v passive), structure, paragraph numbering and indentation, the use of headings, the use of lists, and trademark or branding considerations (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 40–42).

f) Latin Abbreviations and Expressions

I have always known that Latin abbreviations and expressions are accepted in footnotes, bibliographies and informal writing. In my legal background, Latin maxims or phrases are not unusual when enunciating principles of Law. For example, ‘ab initio’ in Latin is used to express ‘from the beginning’ in English. In my comparison between the UK and US language styles, I have used the Latin abbreviation ‘vs’ in this response paper.

The table of acceptable Latin abbreviations and expressions in the study material has widened my knowledge of others I did not know (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 59–64).

g) Paper Review Process

One thing that stood out for me in the EUCLID paper review process is the opportunity it gives students to understand the examiner's mind and what is required of every paper. I have had anxieties over examinations because I am unsure how I would be graded. The study video and the last chapter of the study material explain the use of the Microsoft Word document to review paper responses (Cleenewerck 2016). The premium Grammarly Applications made available to be linked to our working document are an added advantage and a time saver. I have become more confident and will be able to see the comments or corrections made by my examiner.

3) CONCLUSION

The study material has given me a new understanding of how an acceptable international standard paper should look like. I dare to say that a new zeal has been ignited in me to explore further, and I look forward to the rest of the programme. I understood the latest knowledge and refreshed my understanding of the familiar concepts.

I, however, found chapter six (understanding the Chicago style) of the study material too lengthy and exhausting. My response paper shows that not much was mentioned about the chapter. I did not see the need to make it one of the key concepts, as it would seem like a repetition of information already contained in little snippets in the other highlighted concepts (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 43–57). The chapter was well explained but too detailed for this response paper. However, it is of high-priority in this programme, as I do believe that throughout my PhD programme, it will come in handy, as I need to tailor my documents to the style stipulated.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2024. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fifth Edition. Washington D.C: EUCLID University Press.

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